

Stratigraphic Separation of Laacher See Tephra and a Discrete Younger Dryas Boundary Fallout Layer in Southernmost Sweden:

Supporting Information

Christopher R. Moore,^{1,2*} Simon A. Larsson,³ Mohammed Baalousha,⁴ Michael Bizimis,⁵ Mahbub Alam,⁴ Allen West,⁶ Malcolm A. LeCompte,⁷ James P. Kennett,^{8*} Gunther Kletetschka,^{9,10} Julie Chouinard,¹¹ A. Victor Adedeji,¹² Timothy Witwer,⁶

¹South Carolina Institute for Archaeology and Anthropology, University of South Carolina, 1321 Pendleton Street, Columbia, SC 29208, USA; ²SCDNR Heritage Trust Program; Land, Water, and Conservation Division; South Carolina Department of Natural Resources, PO Box 167, Columbia, SC 29202, USA; ³Department of Physical Geography, Stockholm University, SE-10691 Stockholm, Sweden; ⁴Center for Environmental Nanoscience and Risk (CENR), Department of Environmental Health Sciences, Arnold School of Public Health, University of South Carolina, Columbia, 29208, USA; ⁵School of Earth, Ocean and Environment, University of South Carolina, Columbia, SC 29208, USA ⁶Comet Research Group, Prescott, AZ USA; ⁷Center of Excellence in Remote Sensing Education and Research, Elizabeth City State University, Elizabeth City, NC 27921, USA; ⁸Department of Earth Science and Marine Science Institute, University of California Santa Barbara, Santa Barbara, CA, USA; ⁹Geophysical Institute, University of Alaska, Fairbanks, Alaska 99775 USA; ¹⁰Faculty of Science, Charles University, Albertov 6, Prague, 12843, Czech Republic; ¹¹CAMCOR, University of Oregon, 1443 E 13th Ave, Eugene, OR, 97403, USA; ¹²Department of Natural Sciences, Elizabeth City State University, Elizabeth City, NC 27909.

*To whom correspondence should be addressed.

Christopher R. Moore. E-mail: MOORECR@mailbox.sc.edu

James P. Kennett. E-mail: isotope@ucsb.edu

Elemental Maps

Supporting Figure S1. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and elemental map for a complex spherule aggregate from Core KSM 23-5 (spherule peak sample; 281-282 cm) (see Figure 3g in the main paper).

Supporting Figure S2. Optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images for a complex spherule aggregate from Core KSM 23-5 (spherule peak sample; 281-282 cm) (see Figure 3g in the main paper).

Supporting Figure S3. Closeup Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and elemental map for a complex spherule aggregate from Core KSM 23-5 (spherule peak sample; 281-282 cm) (see Figure 3g in the main paper).

Supporting Figure S4. Closeup scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (A) and elemental map (B) for a complex spherule aggregate from Core KSM 23-5 (spherule peak sample; 281-282 cm).

Supporting Figure S5. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and elemental map for a doublet spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (spherule peak sample; 281-282 cm).

Supporting Figure S6. Closeup scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and elemental map of a complex spherule aggregate with spherules held together with Ca-rich micrite/cement from Core KSM 23-5 (spherule peak sample; 281-282 cm).

Supporting Figure S7. Closeup scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and elemental map of a complex spherule aggregate with spherules held together with Ca-rich micrite/cement from Core KSM 23-5 (spherule peak sample; 281-282 cm).

Supporting Figure S8. Optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images for a complex spherule aggregate with a meltglass matrix from Core KSM 23-5 (spherule peak sample; 281-282 cm) (see Figure 3c in the main paper).

EDS Data

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 2,500
 Date : 2025/03/11
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 60.00 sec.
 Real Time : 75.30 sec.
 DeadTime : 20.00 %
 Count Rate : 14447.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	37.67	66.84	0.04	603407	0.8401092	K
Al	1.78	1.88	0.02	48010	0.0214528	K
Si	1.20	1.21	0.02	37819	0.0189166	K
Ca	0.33	0.23	0.01	12449	0.0097744	K
Cr	nd	nd				K
Fe	58.06	29.51	0.07	862079	1.5371649	K
Co*	0.17	0.08	0.03	2108	0.0044307	K
Ni*	0.25	0.12	0.02	2416	0.0060574	K
Mo*	0.32	0.10	0.03	6131	0.0057885	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir*	0.21	0.03	0.05	3134	0.0031966	M
Pt	nd	nd				M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S9. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a dendritic spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (279-280 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001).

001

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 2,700
 Date : 2025/03/11
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

BEC 20kV WD10mm SS62 48Pa x2,700 5µm
 Sample Mar 11, 2025

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time sec. : 60.00
 Real Time sec. : 70.28
 DeadTime : 15.00 %
 Count Rate CPS : 10031.00

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	25.53	54.48	0.04	216536	0.3014786	K
Fe	74.47	45.52	0.11	590321	1.0525949	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S10. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Wüstite spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (279-280 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001).

Volt : 20.00 kV
Mag. : x 1,700
Date : 2025/03/11
Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
Instrument : 6510 (LA)
Volt : 20.00 kV
Current : ---
Process Time : T4
Live time : 60.00 sec.
Real Time : 72.01 sec.
DeadTime : 16.00 %
Count Rate : 12058.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	42.75	60.60	0.04	434873	0.6054636	K
Mg	12.54	11.70	0.03	324538	0.1478252	K
Al	14.88	12.51	0.04	421232	0.1882242	K
Si	6.91	5.58	0.03	190036	0.0950539	K
S	1.27	0.90	0.01	39539	0.0238658	K
Cl	0.26	0.17	0.01	8029	0.0053046	K
K	0.28	0.16	0.01	8482	0.0065650	K
Ca	2.14	1.21	0.02	69399	0.0544891	K
Ti	0.87	0.41	0.02	18720	0.0192840	K
Fe	15.65	6.36	0.04	199114	0.3550377	K
Ba	2.44	0.40	0.04	34086	0.0514717	L
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S11. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich aluminosilicate spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (279-280 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001).

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 1,700
 Date : 2025/03/11
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 60.00 sec.
 Real Time : 72.01 sec.
 DeadTime : 16.00 %
 Count Rate : 12058.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	42.36	60.89	0.04	431746	0.6011099	K
Mg	12.23	11.57	0.03	324531	0.1478218	K
Al	14.46	12.32	0.04	421501	0.1883442	K
Si	6.66	5.45	0.03	189337	0.0947046	K
S	1.23	0.88	0.01	38821	0.0234327	K
Cl	0.26	0.17	0.01	8137	0.0053754	K
K	0.28	0.16	0.01	8479	0.0065625	K
Ca	2.11	1.21	0.02	69404	0.0544928	K
Ti	0.85	0.41	0.02	18720	0.0192840	K
Cr	nd	nd				K
Fe	15.24	6.28	0.04	199104	0.3550204	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni*	0.05	0.02	0.02	420	0.0010521	K
Mo	nd	nd				L
Ru*	0.00	0.00	0.03	27	0.0000242	L
Rh*	0.07	0.02	0.03	1345	0.0012389	L
Pd*	0.13	0.03	0.02	2215	0.0023932	L
Ba	2.39	0.40	0.04	34086	0.0514716	L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir*	1.50	0.18	0.05	18875	0.0192546	M
Pt*	0.19	0.02	0.05	2449	0.0025314	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S12. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich aluminosilicate spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (279-280 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001). Note iridium (Ir) value of 1.5 wt.%.

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 7,000
 Date : 2025/03/11
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 23.83 sec.
 Real Time : 29.28 sec.
 DeadTime : 18.00 %
 Count Rate : 13410.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	46.11	65.66	0.07	218100	0.7645537	K
Mg	10.32	9.67	0.05	114901	0.1317748	K
Al	12.65	10.68	0.05	159976	0.1799854	K
Si	4.66	3.78	0.04	58814	0.0740706	K
S	2.36	1.68	0.02	33747	0.0512873	K
Ca	2.16	1.23	0.02	31891	0.0630443	K
Ti	0.99	0.47	0.03	9656	0.0250437	K
Cr*	0.02	0.01	0.02	165	0.0005522	K
Fe	14.18	5.79	0.06	81487	0.3658379	K
Co*	0.02	0.01	0.03	77	0.0004085	K
Ni*	0.02	0.01	0.03	73	0.0004635	K
Mo	nd	nd				L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd*	0.06	0.01	0.03	458	0.0012455	L
Ba	5.29	0.88	0.07	33546	0.1275437	L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir*	1.17	0.14	0.07	6628	0.0170249	M
Pt	nd	nd				M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S13. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich aluminosilicate spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (279-280 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001). Note iridium (Ir) value of ~1.2 wt.%.

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 7,000
 Date : 2025/03/11
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 38.26 sec.
 Real Time : 45.83 sec.
 DeadTime : 17.00 %
 Count Rate : 11956.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	42.04	59.91	0.05	281783	0.6152426	K
Mg	13.25	12.42	0.04	227911	0.1627995	K
Al	15.73	13.29	0.05	293080	0.2053744	K
Si	7.27	5.90	0.04	130053	0.1020139	K
Ca	1.89	1.07	0.02	39251	0.0483293	K
Cr	nd	nd				K
Fe	16.90	6.90	0.05	140711	0.3934661	K
Co*	0.00	0.00	0.03	31	0.0001020	K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo*	1.36	0.32	0.04	13786	0.0204125	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd*	0.02	0.00	0.03	159	0.0002702	L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir*	1.23	0.15	0.06	9690	0.0155011	M
Pt*	0.31	0.04	0.06	2483	0.0040247	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S14. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich aluminosilicate spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (279-280 cm), showing major element composition (Point 002). Note iridium (Ir) value of ~1.2 wt.%.

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 2,300
 Date : 2025/03/11
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510 (LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 44.80 sec.
 Real Time : 55.16 sec.
 DeadTime : 19.00 %
 Count Rate : 13410.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	35.57	64.03	0.04	370671	0.6911744	K
Al	2.74	2.92	0.03	52714	0.0315466	K
Si	2.64	2.70	0.03	58553	0.0392248	K
Ca	0.95	0.68	0.02	25338	0.0266446	K
Cr*	0.05	0.03	0.01	791	0.0014093	K
Fe	56.98	29.38	0.08	593160	1.4165057	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo*	0.45	0.13	0.04	5866	0.0074180	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd*	0.18	0.05	0.03	2404	0.0034788	L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir*	0.45	0.07	0.05	4617	0.0063083	M
Pt	nd	nd				M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S15. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a FeO spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (279-280 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001). Note iridium (Ir) value of 1.5 wt.%.

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 2,300
 Date : 2025/03/11
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 39.03 sec.
 Real Time : 46.81 sec.
 DeadTime : 16.00 %
 Count Rate : 11647.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	30.85	58.55	0.05	228066	0.4881334	K
Al	3.43	3.86	0.03	49052	0.0336951	K
Si	3.50	3.78	0.03	57309	0.0440667	K
Ca	1.35	1.02	0.02	26686	0.0322107	K
Cr	nd	nd				K
Fe	59.82	32.52	0.10	463953	1.2717441	K
Co*	0.07	0.03	0.04	422	0.0013639	K
Ni*	0.01	0.01	0.03	69	0.0002675	K
Mo*	0.41	0.13	0.04	3925	0.0056973	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir*	0.49	0.08	0.07	3651	0.0057249	M
Pt*	0.08	0.01	0.06	605	0.0009611	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S16. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich aluminosilicate spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (279-280 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001). Note iridium (Ir) value of ~0.5 wt.%.

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 1,100
 Date : 2025/03/11
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 42.96 sec.
 Real Time : 52.51 sec.
 DeadTime : 18.00 %
 Count Rate : 12707.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	36.36	67.35	0.04	354734	0.6897867	K
Cr	nd	nd				K
Fe	60.48	32.09	0.09	552879	1.3768619	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni*	0.05	0.02	0.03	291	0.0010206	K
Mo*	0.28	0.09	0.04	3273	0.0043158	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh*	0.01	0.00	0.03	176	0.0002270	L
Pd*	0.05	0.01	0.03	619	0.0009346	L
Os*	1.49	0.23	0.09	12737	0.0184866	M
Ir*	0.58	0.09	0.06	5326	0.0075887	M
Pt*	0.70	0.11	0.07	6481	0.0093569	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S18. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule cluster within meltglass matrix from Core KSM 23-5 (279-280).cm), showing major element composition (Point 002). Note iridium (Ir) value of ~0.6 wt.%, osmium (Os) value of ~1.5 wt.%, and platinum (Pt) value of 0.7 wt.%.

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 1,100
 Date : 2025/03/11
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 54.97 sec.
 Real Time : 66.51 sec.
 DeadTime : 17.00 %
 Count Rate : 12049.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	29.83	56.51	0.04	323614	0.4917877	K
Mg	1.23	1.54	0.02	20148	0.0100172	K
Al	1.89	2.12	0.02	42669	0.0208108	K
Si	5.83	6.30	0.03	153106	0.0835898	K
Ca	2.48	1.88	0.02	77115	0.0660877	K
Cr*	0.00	0.00	0.01	29	0.0000424	K
Fe	57.95	31.44	0.08	706081	1.3742108	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni*	0.07	0.03	0.02	545	0.0014914	K
Mo*	0.45	0.14	0.03	6889	0.0070992	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd*	0.01	0.00	0.03	227	0.0002677	L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir*	0.10	0.02	0.05	1173	0.0013059	M
Pt*	0.15	0.02	0.05	1770	0.0019969	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S19. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule cluster within meltglass matrix from Core KSM 23-5 (279-280 cm), showing major element composition (Point 003).

001

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 2,000
 Date : 2025/02/25
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time sec. : 21.40
 Real Time sec. : 26.34
 DeadTime : 18.00 %
 Count Rate : 13198.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	41.88	65.71	0.07	166471	0.6498313	K
Na	1.91	2.08	0.04	9304	0.0193437	K
Al	2.66	2.48	0.03	29243	0.0366369	K
Si	10.04	8.97	0.05	124147	0.1741037	K
Ca	6.82	4.27	0.04	91895	0.2022949	K
Fe	36.69	16.49	0.09	191205	0.9558951	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S20. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich aluminosilicate spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (280-281 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001).

002

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 2,000
 Date : 2025/02/25
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 19.60 sec.
 Real Time : 23.12 sec.
 DeadTime : 15.00 %
 Count Rate : 10531.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	22.72	50.65	0.05	87663	0.3736249	K
Fe	77.28	49.35	0.16	282466	1.5418243	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S21. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich aluminosilicate spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (280-281 cm), showing major element composition (Point 002).

001

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 1,900
 Date : 2025/02/25
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time sec. : 11.71
 Real Time sec. : 14.45
 DeadTime : 19.00 %
 Count Rate : 13329.00
 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	38.87	68.94	0.09	103761	0.7402098	K
Fe	61.13	31.06	0.18	141802	1.2955409	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S22. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a FeO dendritic spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (280-281 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001).

001

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 2,000
 Date : 2025/02/25
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time sec. : 31.23
 Real Time sec. : 35.93
 DeadTime : 13.00 %
 Count Rate : 8797.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	18.10	43.59	0.04	93703	0.2506444	K
Fe	79.87	55.08	0.14	403022	1.3806442	K
Ni	2.03	1.33	0.05	6618	0.0318818	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S23. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich dendritic spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (280-281 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001). Note nickel (Ni) value of ~2 wt.%.

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 2,000
 Date : 2025/02/25
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 31.23 sec.
 Real Time : 35.93 sec.
 DeadTime : 13.00 %
 Count Rate : 8797.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	18.07	44.10	0.04	92306	0.2469073	K
Cr*	0.10	0.08	0.02	863	0.0022045	K
Fe	77.01	53.86	0.13	403016	1.3806238	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni	1.94	1.29	0.05	6617	0.0318773	K
Mo*	0.41	0.17	0.05	2576	0.0046732	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Os*	1.42	0.29	0.11	6594	0.0131654	M
Ir*	0.35	0.07	0.08	1724	0.0033782	M
Pt*	0.69	0.14	0.08	3524	0.0069988	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S24. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich dendritic spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (280-281 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001). Note iridium (Ir) value of ~0.35 wt.%, osmium (Os) value of ~1.4 wt.%, and platinum (Pt) value of 0.7 wt.%.

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 950
 Date : 2025/02/25
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510 (LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 28.45 sec.
 Real Time : 35.61 sec.
 DeadTime : 20.00 %
 Count Rate : 14041.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	41.17	72.47	0.06	279123	0.8195772	K
Cr*	0.01	0.00	0.02	55	0.0001545	K
Fe	52.60	26.53	0.10	344166	1.2942281	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni*	0.04	0.02	0.03	157	0.0008310	K
Mo*	0.48	0.14	0.05	3961	0.0078877	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Os*	2.83	0.42	0.12	17836	0.0390895	M
Ir*	1.51	0.22	0.08	10160	0.0218570	M
Pt*	1.37	0.20	0.09	9206	0.0200703	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S25. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich dendritic spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (280-281 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001). Note iridium (Ir) value of ~1.5 wt.%, osmium (Os) value of ~2.8 wt.%, and platinum (Pt) value of 1.4 wt.%.

001

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 1,100
 Date : 2025/02/18
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

BEC 20kV WD10mm SS62 48Pa x1,100 10µm
 Sample Feb 18, 2025

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510 (LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 32.30 sec.
 Real Time : 36.74 sec.
 DeadTime : 12.00 %
 Count Rate : 8028.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	16.99	41.67	0.04	81153	0.2098829	K
Fe	83.01	58.33	0.15	385707	1.2775563	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S26. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich dendritic spherule within a complex spherule aggregate from Core KSM 23-5 (281-282 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001). See elemental map in Supporting Figure S3.

001

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 1,400
 Date : 2025/02/18
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time sec. : 22.82
 Real Time sec. : 27.04
 DeadTime : 16.00 %
 Count Rate : 10891.00
 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	42.62	65.74	0.08	121675	0.4454137	K
Al	4.43	4.05	0.04	46560	0.0547018	K
Si	11.15	9.80	0.06	127607	0.1678206	K
Ca	10.34	6.37	0.05	125753	0.2596040	K
Ti	1.87	0.96	0.03	14615	0.0395839	K
Fe	29.59	13.07	0.09	137675	0.6454516	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S27. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich complex aluminosilicate spherule aggregate from Core KSM 23-5 (281-282 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001).

002

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 1,400
 Date : 2025/02/18
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time sec. : 21.63
 Real Time sec. : 26.14
 DeadTime : 17.00 %
 Count Rate : 12374.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	50.66	71.10	0.09	165539	0.6393221	K
Na	1.36	1.33	0.04	7168	0.0147442	K
Al	4.73	3.94	0.04	54464	0.0675085	K
Si	11.97	9.57	0.06	147973	0.2053110	K
Ca	8.78	4.92	0.04	111784	0.2434625	K
Ti	1.43	0.67	0.02	11708	0.0334556	K
Fe	21.06	8.47	0.08	102669	0.5078163	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S28. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich complex spherule aggregate from Core KSM 23-5 (281-282 cm), showing major element composition (Point 002).

Volt : 20.00 kV
Mag. : x 2,300
Date : 2025/02/18
Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510 (LA)
Volt : 20.00 kV
Current : ---
Process Time : T4
Live time : 47.13 sec.
Real Time : 55.59 sec.
DeadTime : 15.00 %
Count Rate : 10522.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	32.06	58.26	0.04	269982	0.4785348	K
Na	1.62	2.04	0.03	12223	0.0115389	K
Mg	0.64	0.77	0.02	8034	0.0046585	K
Al	2.27	2.45	0.02	39616	0.0225363	K
Si	6.37	6.59	0.04	128137	0.0815946	K
Ca	2.06	1.50	0.02	48706	0.0486848	K
Cr*	0.00	0.00	0.02	54	0.0000915	K
Fe	54.00	28.11	0.08	500177	1.1354061	K
Co*	0.07	0.04	0.04	559	0.0014966	K
Ni*	0.15	0.07	0.03	916	0.0029238	K
Mo*	0.41	0.13	0.04	4783	0.0057491	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Os*	0.15	0.02	0.08	1280	0.0016930	M
Ir*	0.19	0.03	0.06	1691	0.0021956	M
Pt	nd	nd				M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S29. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a FeO spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (281-282 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001).

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 2,500
 Date : 2025/02/18
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 60.00 sec.
 Real Time : 70.41 sec.
 DeadTime : 15.00 %
 Count Rate : 10203.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	42.53	65.48	0.06	225273	0.3136418	K
Al	4.07	3.72	0.02	111277	0.0497234	K
Si	11.60	10.18	0.04	341324	0.1707265	K
Ca	18.58	11.42	0.04	540930	0.4247146	K
Cr*	0.02	0.01	0.01	248	0.0003299	K
Fe	19.46	8.58	0.05	218279	0.3892116	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo*	1.05	0.27	0.04	15575	0.0147053	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd*	0.05	0.01	0.03	738	0.0007979	L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir*	2.21	0.28	0.05	26219	0.0267458	M
Pt*	0.42	0.05	0.05	5115	0.0052871	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S30. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich aluminosilicate spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (281-282 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001). Note iridium (Ir) value of ~2.2 wt.%, molybdenum (Mo) value of ~1 wt.%, and platinum (Pt) of ~0.4 wt.%.

001

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 1,400
 Date : 2025/02/18
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510 (LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time sec. : 17.54
 Real Time sec. : 20.73
 DeadTime : 15.00 %
 Count Rate : 10552.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	40.01	66.29	0.08	110690	0.5271757	K
Si	9.42	8.89	0.07	71002	0.1214867	K
Ca	4.38	2.90	0.04	36561	0.0981975	K
Fe	46.19	21.92	0.13	149406	0.9113007	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S31. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a complex FeSi-rich spherule aggregate from Core KSM 23-5 (281-282 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001).

Volt : 20.00 kV
Mag. : x 1,400
Date : 2025/02/18
Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510(LA)
Volt : 20.00 kV
Current : ---
Process Time : T4
Live time : 17.54 sec.
Real Time : 20.73 sec.
DeadTime : 15.00 %
Count Rate : 10552.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	39.62	66.59	0.08	109314	0.5206229	K
Si	8.99	8.61	0.06	70718	0.1210006	K
Ca	4.28	2.87	0.04	36562	0.0982002	K
Cr	nd	nd				K
Fe	44.54	21.45	0.13	149393	0.9112251	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni*	0.15	0.07	0.04	341	0.0029241	K
Mo*	0.17	0.05	0.06	720	0.0023264	L
Ru*	0.17	0.04	0.05	828	0.0025390	L
Rh*	0.12	0.03	0.05	607	0.0019120	L
Pd*	0.10	0.02	0.05	418	0.0015467	L
Os*	0.62	0.09	0.17	1922	0.0068314	M
Ir*	0.88	0.12	0.11	2921	0.0101930	M
Pt*	0.38	0.05	0.12	1283	0.0045372	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S32. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a complex FeSi-rich spherule aggregate from Core KSM 23-5 (281-282 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001). Note trace amounts of osmium (Os), iridium (Ir), and platinum (Pt).

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 430
 Date : 2025/02/18
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 60.00 sec.
 Real Time : 67.75 sec.
 DeadTime : 13.00 %
 Count Rate : 8187.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	43.13	58.12	0.06	216262	0.3010961	K
Na	1.30	1.21	0.02	17067	0.0126552	K
Al	23.35	18.65	0.05	569009	0.2542569	K
Si	24.95	19.15	0.06	476365	0.2382726	K
Ca	3.56	1.92	0.03	67410	0.0529276	K
Cr	nd	nd				K
Fe*	1.62	0.62	0.03	12425	0.0221548	K
Co*	0.06	0.02	0.02	366	0.0007689	K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo*	0.44	0.10	0.04	3867	0.0036512	L
Ru*	0.00	0.00	0.03	18	0.0000164	L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd*	0.18	0.04	0.03	1650	0.0017826	L
Os*	0.34	0.04	0.12	2123	0.0022066	M
Ir*	0.92	0.10	0.07	6231	0.0063559	M
Pt*	0.17	0.02	0.08	1158	0.0011968	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S33. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a large aluminosilicate spherule within a complex spherule aggregate consisting of thousands of spherules from Core KSM 23-5 (281-282 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001). Note iridium (Ir) value of ~0.9 wt.%.

001

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 2,300
 Date : 2025/02/18
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510 (LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time sec. : 40.93
 Real Time sec. : 48.83
 DeadTime : 16.00 %
 Count Rate : 11620.00
 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	44.68	67.23	0.05	358493	0.7316713	K
Na	1.85	1.93	0.03	14577	0.0158451	K
Al	1.83	1.63	0.02	32255	0.0211280	K
Si	16.31	13.98	0.05	324678	0.2380652	K
Fe	35.33	15.23	0.07	289585	0.7569363	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S34. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich aluminosilicate spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (281-282 cm), showing major element composition (Point 001).

002

Volt : 20.00 kV
 Mag. : x 2,300
 Date : 2025/02/18
 Pixel : 1280 x 960

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time sec. : 28.60
 Real Time sec. : 33.38
 DeadTime : 15.00 %
 Count Rate : 10042.00
 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	33.11	61.23	0.06	173339	0.5062985	K
Al	1.02	1.11	0.03	9290	0.0087085	K
Si	5.24	5.52	0.05	56356	0.0591366	K
Fe	60.64	32.13	0.12	304117	1.1376249	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supporting Figure S35. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a Fe-rich aluminosilicate spherule from Core KSM 23-5 (281-282 cm), showing major element composition (Point 002). Note bright Fe-rich dendritic crystals on left side and secondary impact features on the right side and top.

Area 1

Element Base(7)_pt1 Base(7)_pt1 Base(7)_pt1 Base(7)_pt1 Base(7)_pt1

	Line Type	Weight %	Weight % err	Atom %	Atom % err
O K	K	41.74	0.21	60.04	0.31
Na K	K	1.15	0.02	1.16	0.02
Mg K	K	2.59	0.03	2.45	0.03
Al K	K	8.78	0.05	7.49	0.04
Si K	K	15.06	0.07	12.34	0.05
P K	K	0.59	0.03	0.44	0.02
Cl K	K	0.58	0.02	0.38	0.02
K K	K	0.70	0.03	0.41	0.02
Ca K	K	22.18	0.10	12.74	0.06
Ti K	K	1.33	0.05	0.64	0.02
Fe K	K	3.74	0.11	1.54	0.05
Mo L	L	1.55	0.03	0.37	0.01
		100.00		100.00	

Supporting Information Figure S36. (SEM) and Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) of a complex spherule aggregate with spherules held together with Ca-rich micrite/cement from Core KSM 23-5 (spherule peak sample; 281-282 cm) (Area 1). See Supporting Figure S37 for EDS points 2 and 3.

Pt 2

Element	Base(7)_pt2	Base(7)_pt2	Base(7)_pt2	Base(7)_pt2	Base(7)_pt2
	Line Type	Weight %	Weight % err	Atom %	Atom % err
O K	K	49.97	0.26	70.78	0.37
Mg K	K	0.63	0.02	0.59	0.02
Al K	K	1.17	0.02	0.98	0.02
Si K	K	0.61	0.01	0.49	0.01
P K	K	0.38	0.02	0.28	0.02
S K	K	1.55	0.03	1.09	0.02
Cl K	K	0.17	0.02	0.11	0.02
Ca K	K	45.13	0.18	25.52	0.10
Fe K	K	0.39	0.05	0.16	0.02
		100.00		100.00	

Pt 3

Element	Base(7)_pt3	Base(7)_pt3	Base(7)_pt3	Base(7)_pt3	Base(7)_pt3
	Line Type	Weight %	Weight % err	Atom %	Atom % err
O K	K	23.76	0.19	43.06	0.34
Na K	K	0.24	0.02	0.30	0.02
Mg K	K	0.47	0.01	0.56	0.01
Al K	K	1.49	0.02	1.60	0.02
Si K	K	2.28	0.02	2.35	0.02
P K	K	0.29	0.03	0.27	0.03
S K	K	1.65	0.02	1.49	0.02
Cl K	K	0.10	0.02	0.08	0.01
Ca K	K	68.74	0.28	49.73	0.20
Ti K	K	0.41	0.07	0.25	0.04
Fe K	K	0.56	0.08	0.29	0.04

Supporting Information Figure S37. Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) of a complex spherule aggregate shown in Supporting Figure S36 with spherules held together with Ca-rich micrite/cement from Core KSM 23-5 (spherule peak sample; 281-282 cm) (Points 2 and 3).

Supporting Information Table S1. Radiocarbon ages for Core KSM 23-5. List shows core name, depth (cm), radiocarbon lab number, radiocarbon date, reservoir correction (ΔR), calibrated ages, uncertainties (68.3% and 95.4% CI), references, method, and material. The Bayesian age–depth model was constructed using radiocarbon determinations and stratigraphic ordering only; no constraints based on the position of the microspherule layer or any assumed Younger Dryas Boundary age were applied.

P_Sequence Swedish Lake	Depth	14C age, years BP		Unmodelled (BP)				Modelled (BP)				Amodel 99.4				
		sigma	material	mu	sigma	68_3	68_3	mu	sigma	68_3	68_3	95_4	95_4	A	C	
Outlier_Model General Boundary								-44	62	-47	3	-195	3		99.8	
R_Date UGAMS#73393	273.50	11250	30	sediment	12381	153	12606	12193	12508	99	12605	12460	12620	12200	116.9	99.6
R_Date UGAMS#76082	276.75	11700	40	reed	12818	52	12838	12755	12745	55	12805	12720	12836	12613	113.7	99.6
Delta_R Reservoir-1					800	32	766.5	833.5	789.6	28.3	759.5	816.5	733	848.5	103	99.9
Lithologic transition	277.70								12768	47	12817	12741	12866	12663		99.7
R_Date Ua-66224	278.00	11730	40	reed	12891	87	12960	12762	12775	45	12821	12746	12873	12681	113.1	99.7
Delta_R Reservoir-2					0	0	-0.5	0.5	0	0	-0.5	0.5	-0.5	0.5	100	100
R_Date UGAMS#76083	278.25	10959	70	leaf fragment	12843	65	12889	12762	12780	44	12823	12750	12876	12691	116.9	99.6
C_Date ET element peaks	279.00				12825	50	12877	12774	12825	50	12875	12775	12925	12725		99.9
R_Date UGAMS#73394	279.50	11750	40	sediment	12866	73	12898	12769	12805	45	12844	12760	12899	12716	116.1	99.7
C_Date Spherule peak	281.50				12825	50	12877	12774	12825	50	12875	12775	12925	12725		99.9
R_Date UGAMS#76084	283.25	11970	40	reed	13090	58	13161	13074	12911	49	12971	12885	12996	12806	45	99.7
R_Date UGAMS#76085	285.75	7990	35	bark	8005	57	8027	7956	7983	50	8016	7945	8162	7867		99.9
C_Date LST layer	288.50				13006	9	13017	12995	12989	27	13017	12981	13028	12925	98.6	99.8
R_Date UGAMS#73395	289.50	12020	30	sediment	13134	31	13161	13100	13054	58	13119	12984	13158	12947	88.1	99.5
Delta_R Reservoir-3 Boundary					800	32	766.5	833.5	821.4	32.4	792	856.5	752.5	886	87.4	99.8
U(0,4)					2	1.14	4.0E-17	4	1.32	0.65	0.56	2.23	5.4E-17	2.25	100.00	97.4
Exp(1,-10,0)					-1.05	1.00	-1.24	-0.05	-1.04	0.98						100

Supporting Information Table S2 Operating conditions for inductively coupled plasma-time of flight-mass spectrometer analysis (TOFWERK icpTOF R).

Instrument parameter	Value				
Plasma Power	1550 V				
Nebulizer Gas Flow	1.1-1.14 L/min				
Auxiliary Gas Flow	0.8 L/min				
Cooling Gas Flow	14 L/min				
Injector Diameter	2.5 mm				
Collision Cell Gas	5 mL/min He with 4.5% H ₂				
CCT Bias	-2.50 V				
Notch	Mass	29	32	36.3	41
	Amplitude (V)	1.6	2.0	2.0	1.2
Data acquisition	Continuous Mode				
Detected Mass Range	14-275 m/Z				
TOF Repetition Rate	33 kHz				
TOF Time Resolution	30 μ s				

Integration Time	2 ms
Sample Flow Rate	0.455 mL/min
Transport Efficiency	6.6%
(CeO/Ce)	< 3.0%

Supporting Information Table S3. Elements were monitored for single particle-inductively coupled plasma-time of flight-mass spectrometer analysis and the corresponding particle mass and size detection limits.

Element	Isotope	Mass detection limit (g)	Size detection limit (nm, assuming pure metallic particle)	Size detection limit (nm, assuming pure metal oxide particle)	Metal oxide form
Al	²⁷ Al	6.90×10^{-15}	170	185	Al ₂ O ₃
Ti	⁴⁸ Ti	7.19×10^{-16}	67	82	TiO ₂
V	⁵¹ V	4.20×10^{-16}	51	75	V ₂ O ₅
Cr	⁵² Cr	3.27×10^{-16}	44	56	Cr ₂ O ₃
Mn	⁵⁵ Mn	2.48×10^{-16}	40	53	MnO ₂
Fe	⁵⁶ Fe	8.88×10^{-16}	60	77	Fe ₂ O ₃
Co	⁵⁹ Co	1.99×10^{-16}	35	44	Co ₃ O ₄
Ni	⁶⁰ Ni	8.64×10^{-16}	57	68	NiO
Cu	⁶⁵ Cu	6.66×10^{-16}	52	63	CuO
Zn	⁶⁶ Zn	1.50×10^{-15}	74	86	ZnO
As	⁷⁵ As	1.55×10^{-15}	80	101	As ₂ O ₃
Zr	⁹⁰ Zr	3.29×10^{-16}	46	53	ZrO ₂
Nb	⁹³ Nb	1.56×10^{-16}	33	44	Nb ₂ O ₅
Ru	¹⁰² Ru	4.16×10^{-16}	48	53	RuO ₂
Rh	¹⁰³ Rh	9.51×10^{-17}	30	35	Rh ₂ O ₃
Pd	¹⁰⁶ Pd	5.45×10^{-16}	67	59	PdO
Sn	¹²⁰ Sn	3.25×10^{-16}	44	48	SnO ₂
Sb	¹²¹ Sb	2.61×10^{-16}	42	49	Sb ₂ O ₃
Ba	¹³⁸ Ba	9.50×10^{-17}	37	33	BaO
La	¹³⁹ La	7.29×10^{-17}	28	29	La ₂ O ₃
Ce	¹⁴⁰ Ce	8.63×10^{-17}	29	30	CeO ₂
Pr	¹⁴¹ Pr	6.23×10^{-17}	26	28	Pr ₆ O ₁₁
Nd	¹⁴² Nd	1.70×10^{-16}	36	37	Nd ₂ O ₃
Sm	¹⁵² Sm	2.07×10^{-16}	38	38	Sm ₂ O ₃
Eu	¹⁵³ Eu	1.00×10^{-16}	33	31	Eu ₂ O ₃

Gd	¹⁵⁸ Gd	2.39×10^{-16}	39	41	Gd ₂ O ₃
Tb	¹⁵⁹ Tb	5.26×10^{-17}	23	25	Tb ₄ O ₇
Dy	¹⁶⁴ Dy	1.72×10^{-16}	34	36	Dy ₂ O ₃
Ho	¹⁶⁵ Ho	5.10×10^{-17}	22	24	Ho ₂ O ₃
Er	¹⁶⁶ Er	1.53×10^{-16}	32	34	Er ₂ O ₃
Tm	¹⁶⁹ Tm	5.15×10^{-17}	22	24	Tm ₂ O ₃
Yb	¹⁷⁴ Yb	1.57×10^{-16}	36	33	Yb ₂ O ₃
Lu	¹⁷⁵ Lu	4.38×10^{-17}	20	22	Lu ₂ O ₃
Hf	¹⁸⁰ Hf	1.95×10^{-16}	30	36	HfO ₂
Ta	¹⁸¹ Ta	1.78×10^{-16}	33	42	Ta ₂ O ₅
W	¹⁸⁴ W	3.55×10^{-16}	27	37	WO ₂
Re	¹⁸⁷ Re	1.04×10^{-16}	26	29	ReO ₂
Os	¹⁹² Os	1.20×10^{-16}	27	30	OsO ₂
Ir	¹⁹³ Ir	1.54×10^{-16}	25	32	IrO ₂
Pt	¹⁹⁵ Pt	4.09×10^{-16}	41	45	PtO ₂
Au	¹⁹⁷ Au	2.09×10^{-16}	28	34	Au ₂ O ₃
Pb	²⁰⁸ Pb	1.19×10^{-16}	27	30	PbO
Th	²³² Th	7.64×10^{-17}	23	26	ThO ₂
U	²³⁸ U	6.82×10^{-17}	19	24	UO ₂

The particle mass detection limit is calculated according to the Poisson distribution =

$$Mass_{detection\ limit} = 3.29\sqrt{background\ signal} + 2.71$$

The size detection limit is calculated as the equivalent spherical diameter from the particle mass detection limit, assuming pure metal and metal oxide phases.

Supporting Information Table S4. USGS Reference material BIR-1G data and detection limits.

		BIR1-G average			Reference values	% deviation	Detection limits
	units	(n=7)	STDEV	RSD	(GEOREM)	from Lit	
Na2O wt%	wt%	1.9	0.06	3%	1.85	1%	0.0916
MgO wt%	wt%	9.7	0.43	4%	9.4	3%	0.0160
Al2O3 wt%	wt%	14.5	0.22	2%	15.5	-7%	0.0223
SiO2 wt%	wt%	48.3	0.56	1%	47.5	2%	7.7405
CaO wt%	wt%	12.1	0.56	5%	13.3	-9%	0.2339
Sc	ppm	39.0	0.62	2%	43	-9%	1.5966
TiO2 wt%	wt%	0.9	0.03	3%	1.04	-13%	0.0039
V	ppm	317.4	6.57	2%	326	-3%	0.6232
Cr	ppm	445.1	20.34	5%	392	14%	13.5434
MnO wt%	wt%	0.2	0.01	4%	0.19	-15%	0.0122
FeO wt%	wt%	10.4	0.24	2%	10.4	0%	0.0156
Co	ppm	53.0	1.99	4%	52	2%	0.6268
Ni	ppm	197.1	7.06	4%	178	11%	8.7188
Cu	ppm	144.6	6.52	5%	119	21%	0.9511
Zn	ppm	68.9	2.06	3%	78	-12%	3.4550
Rb	ppm	0.3	0.05	17%	0.197	33%	0.1189
Sr	ppm	107.4	3.90	4%	109	-1%	0.2367
Y	ppm	13.0	0.45	3%	14.3	-9%	0.0287
Zr	ppm	12.3	0.12	1%	14	-12%	1.7960
Nb	ppm	0.5	0.02	4%	0.52	-1%	0.0049
Mo	ppm	0.103	0.02	22%	0.075	37%	0.0402
Rh	ppm	0.005	0.00	77%	not reported		0.0036
Pd	ppm	0.060	0.03	45%	not reported		0.0458
Ba	ppm	6.608	0.15	2%	6.5	2%	1.2978
La	ppm	0.575	0.02	4%	0.609	-6%	0.0013
Ce	ppm	1.928	0.04	2%	1.89	2%	0.0012
Nd	ppm	2.259	0.10	5%	2.37	-5%	0.0061
Sm	ppm	1.061	0.10	9%	1.09	-3%	0.0406
Gd	ppm	1.632	0.07	4%	1.85	-12%	0.1237
Dy	ppm	2.232	0.08	4%	2.55	-12%	0.0031
Er	ppm	1.523	0.08	5%	1.7	-10%	0.0033
Yb	ppm	1.462	0.06	4%	1.64	-11%	0.0095
Hf	ppm	0.472	0.06	13%	0.57	-17%	0.0044
Re	ppm	0.001	0.00	77%	0.00053	143%	0.0007
Ir	ppm	0.006	0.00	76%	not reported		0.0018
Pt	ppm	0.904	0.07	7%	0.92	-2%	0.0022
Pb	ppm	3.655	0.23	6%	3.7	-1%	0.0159
Th	ppm	0.026	0.00	15%	0.03	-14%	0.0002
U	ppm	0.018	0.00	16%	0.023	-21%	0.0001

Supporting Information Table S5. Laacher See Tephra (LST) and microspherule abundance (per/kg).

Depth (cmbs) Midpoint	^a Sample wet weight (g)	Glass shard count	Tephra/kg	^b Sample wet weight (g)	Spherule count	Spherules/kg
268.5				17.861	0	0
269.5				13.275	0	0
270.5				16.478	0	0
271.5				16.1	0	0
272.5				13.268	0	0
273.5				16.544	0	0
274.5				16.151	0	0
275.5				18.988	0	0
276.5				18.088	0	0
277.5				16.729	0	0
278.5				18.107	0	0
279.5				20.897	~15	~700
280.5	1.561	0	0	14.469	~25	~1,800
281.5	1.521	0	0	18.224	~1300	~72,000
282.5	1.396	0	0	18.511	0	0
283.5	1.365	0	0	14.769	0	0
284.5	1.666	0	0	17.016	0	0
285.5	1.375	0	0	16.354	0	0
286.5	1.042	2	1920	18.877	0	0
287.5	1.398	4	2857	16.787	0	0
288.5	1.421	135	96,429	19.527	0	0
289.5	1.090	87	62,100	18.411	0	0
290.5	1.274	1	800	17.344	0	0
291.5	1.232	2	1,630	15.763	0	0
292.5				19.734	0	0
293.5				19.11	0	0
294.5				21.239	0	0
295.5				19.475	0	0
296.5				18.165	0	0
297.5				18.861	0	0
298.5				21.756	0	0
299.5				20.139	0	0
300.5				16.713	0	0
301.5				22.335	0	0
302.5				22.657	0	0

^aSample wet weight for tephra analysis.

^bSample wet weight for spherule analysis.

Microspherule range

LST peak

Supporting Information Table S6. Bayesian analysis of calibrated radiocarbon dates from Krslttamossen fen (Core KSM 23-5), interpolated at 0.5-cm intervals.

z (cmbs)	mu	sigma	sed	from_68_3	to_68_3	from_95_4	to_95_4
260	12047	139	0.0293	12171	12018	12166	11570
260.5	12064	137	0.0293	12187	12034	12183	11593
261	12081	134	0.0293	12203	12051	12200	11616
261.5	12098	132	0.0293	12220	12067	12217	11640
262	12115	129	0.0293	12236	12083	12233	11663
262.5	12132	127	0.0293	12252	12100	12250	11686
263	12149	125	0.0293	12268	12116	12267	11710
263.5	12166	123	0.0293	12284	12133	12284	11733
264	12183	121	0.0293	12300	12149	12301	11756
264.5	12200	119	0.0293	12316	12165	12317	11780
265	12217	117	0.0293	12332	12182	12334	11803
265.5	12234	115	0.0293	12348	12198	12351	11827
266	12252	113	0.0293	12364	12214	12368	11850
266.5	12269	112	0.0293	12380	12231	12385	11873
267	12286	110	0.0293	12396	12247	12401	11897
267.5	12303	108	0.0293	12412	12264	12418	11920
268	12320	107	0.0293	12428	12280	12435	11943
268.5	12337	106	0.0293	12444	12296	12452	11967
269	12354	105	0.0293	12460	12313	12469	11990
269.5	12371	104	0.0293	12477	12329	12486	12013
270	12388	103	0.0293	12493	12345	12502	12037
270.5	12405	102	0.0293	12509	12362	12519	12060
271	12422	101	0.0293	12525	12378	12536	12083
271.5	12439	101	0.0293	12541	12395	12553	12107
272	12456	100	0.0293	12557	12411	12570	12130
272.5	12473	100	0.0293	12573	12427	12586	12153
273	12490	100	0.0293	12589	12444	12603	12177
273.5	12508	99	0.014	12605	12460	12620	12200
274	12544	103	0.0135	12638	12467	12743	12279
274.5	12581	105	0.0136	12699	12521	12779	12344
275	12617	102	0.0135	12732	12552	12801	12406
275.5	12654	96	0.0138	12786	12596	12814	12460
276	12691	85	0.0132	12788	12644	12825	12512
276.5	12727	68	0.0136	12801	12696	12831	12575
277	12751	53	0.0413	12808	12726	12841	12621
277.5	12763	49	0.0419	12815	12736	12861	12651
278	12775	45	0.047	12821	12746	12873	12681
278.5	12785	44	0.0483	12827	12752	12880	12695
279	12795	45	0.0506	12836	12756	12890	12704
279.5	12805	45	0.0404	12844	12760	12899	12716
280	12819	49	0.0355	12867	12773	12921	12725
280.5	12833	51	0.0354	12886	12786	12938	12734
281	12847	53	0.0358	12904	12799	12952	12746
281.5	12861	54	0.0357	12922	12816	12965	12755
282	12875	53	0.0358	12936	12832	12975	12768
282.5	12890	52	0.035	12949	12848	12983	12781
283	12904	50	0.0363	12966	12874	12992	12797
283.5	12914	49	0.0671	12975	12887	12998	12809
284	12922	47	0.0653	12980	12895	13002	12820
284.5	12929	46	0.067	12985	12905	13006	12831
285	12937	45	0.0682	12990	12915	13009	12839
285.5	12944	43	0.066	12996	12924	13012	12851
286	12952	41	0.0679	13000	12933	13015	12863
286.5	12959	39	0.0673	13005	12941	13019	12873
287	12966	37	0.0672	13009	12950	13021	12886
287.5	12974	34	0.0675	13012	12961	13024	12897
288	12981	31	0.0661	13015	12970	13026	12912
288.5	12989	28	0.0253	13017	12981	13028	12925
289	13021	51	0.0151	13097	12970	13139	12929
289.5	13054	58	0.0163	13119	12984	13158	12947
290	13071	58	0.0293	13135	13000	13175	12970
290.5	13088	59	0.0293	13151	13017	13192	12994
291	13105	59	0.0293	13167	13033	13206	13017
291.5	13122	60	0.0293	13183	13050	13225	13040
292	13139	61	0.0293	13199	13066	13242	13064
292.5	13156	62	0.0293	13215	13082	13259	13087
293	13173	63	0.0293	13231	13099	13276	13110
293.5	13190	65	0.0293	13248	13115	13293	13134
294	13207	67	0.0293	13264	13131	13309	13157
294.5	13224	68	0.0293	13280	13148	13326	13180
295	13242	70	0.0293	13296	13164	13343	13204
295.5	13259	73	0.0293	13312	13181	13360	13227
296	13276	75	0.0293	13328	13197	13377	13250
296.5	13293	77	0.0293	13344	13213	13393	13274
297	13310	79	0.0293	13360	13230	13410	13297
297.5	13327	82	0.0293	13376	13246	13427	13321
298	13344	84	0.0293	13392	13262	13444	13344
298.5	13361	87	0.0293	13408	13279	13461	13367
299	13378	90	0.0293	13424	13295	13477	13391
299.5	13395	93	0.0293	13440	13312	13494	13414
300	13412	95	0.0293	13456	13328	13511	13437
300.5	13429	98	0.0293	13472	13344	13528	13461
301	13446	101	0.0293	13488	13361	13545	13484
301.5	13463	104	0.0293	13505	13377	13562	13507
302	13480	107	0.0293	13521	13393	13578	13531
302.5	13498	110	0.0293	13537	13410	13595	13554
303	13515	113	0.0293	13553	13426	13612	13577
303.5	13532	116	0.0293	13569	13443	13629	13601
304	13549	120	0.0293	13585	13459	13646	13624
304.5	13566	123	0.0293	13601	13475	13662	13647
305	13583	126	0.0293	13617	13492	13679	13671

Supporting Information Table S7. SP-ICP-TOF-MS nanoparticle data for Körslättamossen bulk sediments.

<https://zenodo.org/records/17954219>

Supporting Information Table S8. Laser ablation ICP-MS data for Körslättamossen microspherules (279-282 cm).

	Oxide/element	Total wt%	KSM 23-5_1	KSM 23-5_4	KSM 23-5_6	KSM 23-5_3_30	KSM 23-5_2_31
Na23(LR)	Na2O	wt%	2.011	3.933	1.479	761.55	855.23
Mg25(LR)	MgO	wt%	0.309	2.351	0.507	6754.16	2363.59
Al27(LR)	Al2O3	wt%	41.384	14.197	9.250	25398.34	4989.64
Si29(LR)	SiO2	wt%	52.504	56.203	29.807	62665.55	25377.20
Ca43(LR)	CaO	wt%	2.332	20.039	1.718	45025.22	13445.24
Sc45(LR)	Sc	ppm	2.271	13.647	3.854	3.40	0.83
Ti47(LR)	Ti	ppm	526.885	9321.845	1293.544	1494.01	434.63
V51(LR)	V	ppm	9.558	107.115	43.025	46.34	16.74
Cr53(LR)	Cr	ppm	6.994	24.498	33.591	15.72	23.29
Mn55(LR)	MnO	wt%	0.003	0.014	0.006	127.32	56.65
Fe57(LR)	FeO	wt%	0.458	2.264	56.233	857665.61	951948.32
Co59(LR)	Co	ppm	-0.215	19.362	6.732	14.32	20.95
Ni60(LR)	Ni	ppm	26.251	55.926	20.829	32.53	44.25
Cu63(LR)	Cu	ppm	74.330	198.328	152.231	247.26	201.34
Zn66(LR)	Zn	ppm	33.229	205.357	32.499	244.63	287.45
Rb85(LR)	Rb	ppm	18.660	51.569	6.767	0.00	0.31
Sr88(LR)	Sr	ppm	124.381	1051.894	347.694	432.85	255.99
Y89(LR)	Y	ppm	2.200	35.479	6.111	6.47	8.80
Zr90(LR)	Zr	ppm	7.814	207.520	28.877	46.53	15.20
Nb93(LR)	Nb	ppm	1.878	25.120	4.468	7.29	1.54
Mo98(LR)	Mo	ppm	-0.118	4.270	-0.068	0.45	0.21
Ba137(LR)	Ba	ppm	388.335	2316.089	875.081	734.34	973.82
La139(LR)	La	ppm	2.619	65.028	15.223	7.80	4.43
Ce140(LR)	Ce	ppm	6.783	110.746	25.285	15.74	12.65
Nd146(LR)	Nd	ppm	2.237	42.724	10.190	6.06	5.26
Sm147(LR)	Sm	ppm	0.432	7.839	1.955	1.54	1.58
Gd157(LR)	Gd	ppm	0.904	6.671	1.109	1.45	1.51
Dy163(LR)	Dy	ppm	0.300	5.464	1.005	1.09	1.33
Er167(LR)	Er	ppm	0.266	3.293	1.081	0.75	0.62
Yb172(LR)	Yb	ppm	0.043	5.849	0.678	0.57	0.48
Hf178(LR)	Hf	ppm	0.266	4.854	0.603	1.51	0.30
Pt195(LR)	Pt	ppm	0.067	0.097	9.822	0.51	0.87
Pb208(LR)	Pb	ppm	16.944	39.177	27.767	4.39	4.99
Th232(LR)	Th	ppm	0.713	15.438	2.876	4.31	1.43
U238(LR)	U	ppm	0.499	5.539	1.299	2.54	1.24

Supporting Information Table S9. ICP-MS data (Actlabs Ultratrace 6) for Körslättamossen bulk sediments.

<https://zenodo.org/records/17954219>

Supporting Information Table S10. ET comparative data.

Name Label	ET Category	Ratio	YDB Depth	YDB Ratio	ET Ratio	Qualitative score	Chondrite	factor	ET_ID	ET_Name
RMNs, Pt/Fe, 281.5	RMNs	Pt/Fe	281.5	113000	113108	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.000957	1780	Murchison
RMNs, Pt/Fe, 280.5	RMNs	Pt/Fe	280.5	79600	79589.9	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.000127	1868	Murchison
IDPs, Ni/Fe, 279.5	IDPs	Ni/Fe	279.5	370.88	371.403	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.00141	156	IDPs, stratosphere
IDPs, Ni/Fe, 279.5	IDPs	Ni/Fe	279.5	370.88	369.09	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.00485	216	IDPs, stratosphere
Lunar, Cr/Ni, 278.5	Lunar	Cr/Ni	278.5	116	118.677	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.023081	1011	Yamato 793274; 981031
Lunar, Cr/Ni, 278.5	Lunar	Cr/Ni	278.5	116	118.677	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.02308	1004	Lunar, #8
IDPs, Cr/Fe, 279.5	IDPs	Cr/Fe	279.5	47.3	47.2608	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.00083	294	IDPs, stratosphere
IDPs, Cr/Fe, 281.5	IDPs	Cr/Fe	281.5	47	47.2608	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.005549	294	IDPs, stratosphere
MMs, Cr/Fe, 280.5	MMs	Cr/Fe	280.5	31.4	30.8978	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.016255	1195	Micrometeorite
MMs, Cr/Fe, 280.5	MMs	Cr/Fe	280.5	31.4	29.1432	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.077437	1142	Micrometeorite
MMs, Cr/Fe, 280.5	MMs	Cr/Fe	280.5	31.4	28.7553	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.091973	1194	Micrometeorite
Comet, Cr/Fe, 280.5	Comet	Cr/Fe	280.5	31.4	28.5172	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.101089	45	Comet Wild 2
Martian, Cr/Co, 278.5	Martian	Cr/Co	278.5	17.4	18.202	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.046091	1018	Martian
Martian, Cr/Co, 278.5	Martian	Cr/Co	278.5	17.4	18.202	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.046091	1012	ALH 77005 Shergottite
Lunar, Co/Ni, 278.5	Lunar	Co/Ni	278.5	6.66	7.66633	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.1511	1001	Lunar, #3
Lunar, Co/Ni, 278.5	Lunar	Co/Ni	278.5	6.66	7.66633	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.1511	1008	Yamato 793274; 981031
Iron, Co/Ni, 278.5	Iron	Co/Ni	278.5	6.66	6.71326	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.007997	753	Canyon Diablo
Martian, Co/Ni, 278.5	Martian	Co/Ni	278.5	6.66	6.56115	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.015067	1023	Martian
Martian, Co/Ni, 278.5	Martian	Co/Ni	278.5	6.66	6.56115	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.015067	1017	LAR 06319
RMNs, Ir/Pt, 280.5	RMNs	Ir/Pt	280.5	2.39	2.39075	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.000313	1763	Murchison
Iron, Ir/Pt, 280.5	Iron	Ir/Pt	280.5	2.39	2.38097	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.003795	925	Iron, Negrillos, bulk
Iron, Ir/Pt, 280.5	Iron	Ir/Pt	280.5	2.39	2.38097	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.003795	792	iron
Iron, Ir/Pt, 280.5	Iron	Ir/Pt	280.5	2.39	2.37091	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.008052	923	Iron, Cape of Good Hope
Achondrite, Ir/Pt, 278.5	Achondrite	Ir/Pt	278.5	1.1	1.11018	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.00925	365	achondrite, aubrite
RMNs, Ir/Pt, 278.5	RMNs	Ir/Pt	278.5	1.1	1.09939	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.000556	1562	Allende; CAI A39
Chondrite, Ir/Pt, 278.5	Chondrite	Ir/Pt	278.5	1.1	1.09853	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.001334	581	Chondrites, CB-metal
Chondrite, Ir/Pt, 278.5	Chondrite	Ir/Pt	278.5	1.1	1.09853	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.001334	582	Chondrites, CB-metal
Ureilite, Ir/Pt, 278.5	Ureilite	Ir/Pt	278.5	1.1	1.09798	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.001844	1035	ALHA77257
Ureilite, Ir/Pt, 278.5	Ureilite	Ir/Pt	278.5	1.1	1.08134	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.017257	1041	ALHA82130
MMs, Ir/Pt, 278.5	MMs	Ir/Pt	278.5	1.1	1.00672	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.092662	1091	Chondritic Sphere CH27
Achondrite, Pt/Os, 278.5	Achondrite	Pt/Os	278.5	0.84	0.83948	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.00062	399	ALH 84007
Comet, Pt/Os, 278.5	Comet	Pt/Os	278.5	0.84	0.8394	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.000714	73	PGE Nugget
Achondrite, Pt/Os, 278.5	Achondrite	Pt/Os	278.5	0.84	0.83836	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.001953	317	achondrite, aubrite
Chondrite, Pt/Os, 278.5	Chondrite	Pt/Os	278.5	0.84	0.8355	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.005391	591	Chondrites, CO
Chondrite, Pt/Os, 278.5	Chondrite	Pt/Os	278.5	0.84	0.8355	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.005391	592	Chondrites, CO
Ureilite, Pt/Os, 278.5	Ureilite	Pt/Os	278.5	0.84	0.83411	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.007061	1042	ALHA82130
Ureilite, Pt/Os, 278.5	Ureilite	Pt/Os	278.5	0.84	0.83282	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.008625	1066	Kenna
Achondrite, Pt/Os, 278.5	Achondrite	Pt/Os	278.5	0.84	0.82652	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.01631	356	achondrite, aubrite
Comet, Pt/Os, 278.5	Comet	Pt/Os	278.5	0.84	0.81471	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.031039	12	Comet Wild 2
Comet, Pt/Os, 278.5	Comet	Pt/Os	278.5	0.84	0.81471	Strong \leq 2 \times	1	1.031039	11	Comet Wild 2

Bayesian code

Options()

{

Curve="IntCal20.14c";

};

Plot()

{

Outlier_Model("General",Exp(1,-10,0),U(0,4),"t");

```
P_Sequence("Swedish Lake",0.5,10)
{
Boundary();

Delta_R("Reservoir-3",800,32);
R_Date("UGAMS#73395",12020,30){z=289.5;Outlier("General",1)};
C_Date("LST layer",calBP(13006),9){z=288.5;Outlier("General",1);color="red"};
R_Date("UGAMS#76085",7990,35){z=285.75;Outlier()};
R_Date("UGAMS#76084",11970,40){z=283.25;Outlier("General",1)};
C_Date("Spherule peak",calBP(12825),50){z=281.5;Outlier();color="orange"};
R_Date("UGAMS#73394",11750,40){z=279.5;Outlier("General",1)};
C_Date("ET element peaks",calBP(12825),50){z=279;Outlier();color="orange"};
R_Date("UGAMS#76083",11730,40){z=278.25;Outlier("General",1)};
Delta_R("Reservoir-2",0,0);
R_Date("Ua-66224",10959,70){z=278;Outlier("General",1)};
Date("Lithologic transition"){z=277.7;Outlier();color="orange"};
Delta_R("Reservoir-1",800,32);
R_Date("UGAMS#76082",11700,40){z=276.75;Outlier("General",1)};
R_Date("UGAMS#73393",11250,30){z=273.5;Outlier("General",1)};

Boundary();

};

};
```

Supporting Information: Detailed Methods

Bulk Geochemistry (Ultratrace 6 ICP-MS)

Sediment samples (~0.5 g) were dried, homogenized, and digested using a four-acid near-total dissolution (HF–HClO₄–HNO₃–HCl) at Activation Laboratories (Actlabs, Ontario). The Ultratrace 6™ package quantifies 56 major, trace, and platinum-group elements using high-sensitivity ICP-MS. Calibration employed multi-element standards with drift correction and dynamic range optimization. Detection limits for most elements fall in the sub-ppb to low-ppb range.

Quality assurance included blanks, duplicates, and certified reference materials (OREAS, CANMET, USGS). Analytical precision is typically ±5% RSD for trace elements and ±10% for ultra-trace species. The four-acid digestion efficiently dissolves refractory phases relevant for PGE assessment.

Microspherule Extraction, Identification, and Enumeration

Samples were disaggregated in sodium metaphosphate and ultrasonicated for 30 minutes, then wet-sieved at 20 μm and dried. Fractions (≥63–<125 μm; ≥20–<63 μm) were magnetically separated using a grade-52 NdFeB magnet passed three times over the sample surface. Magnetic and non-magnetic aliquots were inspected under a stereomicroscope.

Candidate microspherules were mounted on carbon tape and confirmed by SEM and EDS following established protocols¹. Identified microspherules were counted and normalized to microspherules kg⁻¹ dry sediment.

Scanning Electron Microscopy and EDS Microanalysis

SEM–EDS analyses were performed at:

1. **Elizabeth City State University (NC)** – JEOL-6000 SEM operated in low vacuum for imaging and qualitative chemistry (±10% major-element uncertainty).
2. **EMSAL, University of Utah** – higher-resolution imaging and minor-element characterization.

Analytical settings, beam conditions, and calibration procedures are fully described in SI Tables.

Single-Particle ICP–TOF–MS (Nanoparticle Quantification)

Sample Preparation. ~100 mg of sediment were suspended in ultrapure water (Millipore), vortexed, ultrasonicated (Branson 2800, 40 kHz, 15 min), and allowed to settle for 24 h. The upper 5 mL was decanted into acid-washed tubes and stored at 4 °C. Prior to analysis, suspensions were diluted 5000× and sonicated before and after dilution.

Instrumentation. SP-ICP-TOF-MS analyses used a TOFWERK instrument with:

- 2DX autosampler (Elemental Scientific)
- MicroMist U-series nebulizer
- Quartz cyclonic spray chamber
- 4.5% H₂/He collision gas to enhance Fe and Si signals

Operating parameters and monitored isotopes are listed in Tables S2–S3 ²⁻⁴.

Calibration and Data Reduction. Calibration employed multi-element ICP solutions (0–10 µg L⁻¹ in 1% HNO₃) and NIST RM 8013 Au nanoparticles for transport efficiency via the known-size method ⁵. Data were processed using TOFpilot v2.11.3 with Poisson thresholding ⁶. Samples and blanks were run in triplicate (200 s each), and replicates were combined.

Nanoparticle masses, counts, and elemental ratios were extracted following established SP-ICP-TOF-MS workflows, with false-positive filtering and event-overlap correction.

Laser ablation ICP-MS (Microspherule Composition)

Microspherule compositions were determined by LA-ICP-MS at the Center for Elemental Mass Spectrometry (CEMS), University of South Carolina, using a Photon Machines 193 nm excimer laser (HELIX-2 cell, He atmosphere) coupled to a Thermo Element 2 HR-ICP-MS. Handpicked microspherules were mounted on tape-covered glass slides; each was ablated with a 40–50 µm beam at 8 Hz for ~20 s (fluence ~11 J/cm²). Beam interaction with tape and substrate was evaluated prior to analysis, and all signal intervals were manually screened to exclude non-spherule material.

Monitored isotopes ranged from major (Na–Si–Fe) to trace and HSE/PGE elements (Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Rb–U; full list in Table S3). Data reduction followed ⁷ and ⁸. The assumption of Fe ≈ 99 wt% for metal-rich microspherules was validated by total-sum closure of 99.4–100.7%. Microspherules were fully consumed during analysis, precluding duplicates.

Concentrations were calibrated using RSFs derived from NIST SRM 612, and USGS reference glasses BCR-2G and BIR-1G. All signals were gas-blank-subtracted and corrected for instrumental drift. Additional instrument parameters and the full analytical workflow are provided in Supporting Information Table S3.

Data and Code Availability

All SEM/TEM images, bulk geochemistry, microspherule counts, SP-ICP-TOF-MS nanoparticle data, laser-ablation results, and OxCal modeling files are provided in the Supporting Information and public repository.

- 1 LeCompte, M. A. *et al.* Independent evaluation of conflicting microspherule results from different investigations of the Younger Dryas impact hypothesis. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **109**, E2960–2969 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1208603109>
- 2 Alam, M. *et al.* Identification and quantification of Cr, Cu, and As incidental nanomaterials derived from CCA-treated wood in wildland-urban interface fire ashes. *J Hazard Mater* **445**, 130608 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.130608>
- 3 Baalousha, M., Wang, J., Erfani, M. & Goharian, E. Elemental fingerprints in natural nanomaterials determined using SP-ICP-TOF-MS and clustering analysis. *Sci Total Environ* **792**, 148426 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.148426>
- 4 Wang, J., Nabi, M. M., Erfani, M., Goharian, E. & Baalousha, M. Identification and quantification of anthropogenic nanomaterials in urban rain and runoff using single particle-inductively coupled plasma-time of flight-mass spectrometry. *Environmental Science: Nano* **9**, 714–729 (2022).
- 5 Pace, H. E. *et al.* Determining transport efficiency for the purpose of counting and sizing nanoparticles via single particle inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry. *Anal Chem* **83**, 9361–9369 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac201952t>
- 6 Gundlach-Graham, A., Hendriks, L., Mehrabi, K. & Gunther, D. Monte Carlo Simulation of Low-Count Signals in Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry and Its Application to Single-Particle Detection. *Anal Chem* **90**, 11847–11855 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.8b01551>
- 7 Frisby, C., Bizimis, M. & Mallick, S. Seawater-derived rare earth element addition to abyssal peridotites during serpentinization. *Lithos* **248**, 432–454 (2016).
- 8 Humayun, M., Simon, S. B. & Grossman, L. Tungsten and hafnium distribution in calcium–aluminum inclusions (CAIs) from Allende and Efremovka. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* **71**, 4609–4627 (2007).